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CREATIVE INDUSTRIES OF RUSSIA AS A VECTOR OF ECONOMIC GROWTH AND EMPLOYMENT

Abstract. Creative industries are one of the key vectors of sustainable economic growth and a condition that opens potential opportunities for effective employment. The use of creative industries as a resource base for the innovative development of Russia is defined by the dynamic implementation of activities related to the realization of the provisions of the concept. The study analyzes the contribution of Russia's creative economy to GDP among BRICS+ countries, and the state of export of creative industry products in Russia. It includes the overview of the top 15 Russian regions in terms of the economic development of creative industries and the share of employees engaged in creative sector organizations. The calculation of the employment workload coefficient in creative industries made it possible to assess their impact on the process of employment of the population. The study established that the key mainstreams that allow creative industries to actively develop are quite an effective tool aimed at the optimal socio-economic development of Russia as a whole and its constituent entities, in particular. Cooperation between government agencies, representatives of creative industries, as well as other ecosystem elements will serve as a basis for implementation of significant creative projects.

Keywords: creative industries, economic growth, population employment, creative entrepreneurship, creative class, creative profession, cultural progress

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КРЕАТИВНЫЕ ИНДУСТРИИ РОССИИ КАК ВЕКТОР ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА И ЗАНЯТОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Креативные индустрии представляют собой значимый вектор устойчивого экономического роста и условие, открывающее потенциальные возможности для эффективной занятости населения. Использование креативных индустрий в качестве ресурсной базы для инновационного развития России определено динамическим осуществлением мероприятий, которые связаны с исполнением положений «Концепции развития творческих (креативных) индустрий и механизмов осуществления их государственной поддержки в крупных и крупнейших городских агломерациях до 2030 года». В исследовании изучен вклад креативной экономики России в ВВП среди стран БРИКС+, доля занятого населения в креативных индустриях, состояние экспорта товаров креативных индустрий России (печатная продукция, дизайнерские товары, товары для новых медиа, художественные промыслы и прочее); представлен топ-15 российских регионов по уровню экономического развития креативных индустрий и доле сотрудников, занятых в ведущих организациях сектора креативных индустрий. Расчет коэффициента нагрузки занятых в креативных индустриях дал возможность оценить их положительное воздействие на процесс трудоустройства населения. В процессе исследования установлено, что ключевые мейнстримы, позволяющие креативным индустриям активно развиваться, представляют собой достаточно эффективный инструмент, направленный на оптимальное социально-экономическое развитие России в целом и ее субъектов в частности. Сотрудничество между государственными органами, представителями креативных индустрий, а также иными экосистемными элементами креативной индустрии послужит основой для реализации существенных креативных проектов.

Ключевые слова: креативные индустрии, экономический рост, занятость населения, креативное предпринимательство, креативный класс, творческая профессия, культурный прогресс

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Introduction

Russia's creative economy, the structure of which includes creative spheres of activity whose ideas are transformed into cultural goods and services (cultural economy, creative industry, goods, services or developments related to the cultural sector), actively influences the development and support of domestic entrepreneurship, stimulates the introduction of innovative, in particular, digital technologies, creates jobs, and opens up potential opportunities for the country as a whole and for its subjects, in particular.

Taking into account the conditions of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development approved by the world community¹, the creative economy itself is a significant benchmark of sustainable development, which is confirmed by the development strategies and concepts of support for the creative economy developed and approved at the state level.

At the same time, in some countries, a significant share of value-added of creative industries is formed by the management of intellectual property rights and active creative activity, has taken on an important purpose as economic growth, cultural progress, and a stimulus for innovation.

The aim of this study is to examine the creative industries of Russia as a fundamental vector for economic growth and employment.

Background

In the current conditions of development, there is a growing interest among researchers in both domestic and international academic circles in studying the characteristics of the creative economy and creative industries. A number of works present the results of a comprehensive analysis of the development indicators of global and Russian creative industry markets. For instance, T. S. Zaitseva emphasized the place of creative industries in the innovative development of the Russian economy [4]. At the same time, I. B. Koroleva and I. L. Sokolova paid attention to specific groups of problems

(legislative, institutional, coordination, etc.) in management and development of the creative economy [6]. The highlight of E. R. Bajkova's work was the experiences of several foreign countries in applying various tools to support the creative sector, and also models that allow creative industries to develop actively [1]. V. N. Kurochkin's research is devoted to increasing the potential of creative service industries, describing their place in filling the GDP [7]. In her research, Y. V. Petrasheuskaya presented a comparative analysis of creative (artistic) and traditional employment, identified the unique aspects of creative labor, reviewed a classification of professions within creative industries, and calculated the number of creative workers in the Republic of Belarus [9].

A significant portion of research focuses on the role of creative industries in the development of regional economy, as well as their inversion on the example of particular Russian regions. Scholars N. V. Sopina, I. V. Klimova, and L. N. Semerkova attempted to establish the relationship between the level of development of creative industries in particular Russian regions and the level of innovative development of these regions [5; 11]. O. N. Naumova focused on the nature and characteristics of creative industries clusters in the regional economy [8]. A. S. Efimova and N. V. Bryukhanova analyzed the circumstances of creative industries development in the Southern Federal District [3], while M. Yu. Vakhovskaya conducted an analysis of the prospects for developing creative (artistic) industries in the Republic of Crimea and proposed measures to promote the growth of creative sectors [2]. L. D. Saifullina emphasized cultural and creative sectors of the economy of the Republic of Bashkortostan, highlighted the directions of their support and prospective development [10].

Foreign researchers have also made significant contributions to the study of creative industries. Scholars from the University of Valencia (Spain), Rafael Boix-Domenech, Jesús Peiro-Palomino, and Pau Rausell-Köster [13], described the impact of creative industries on the development of leading

1 Agenda for Sustainable Development until 2030. 2015. URL: https://www.economy.gov.ru/material/directions/vneshneekonomicheskaya_deyatelnost/ustoychivoe_razvitiye/povestka_2030_i_cur_oon/ (Accessed on September 11, 2024) (In Russ.).

European regions, demonstrating that the growth of these industries directly influences labor productivity levels. Christiaan De Beukelaer [12] from the University of Leeds (UK), taking into account UNCTAD reports, studied the development of creative industries in developing countries and classified them by the level of development of creative economy; scholar Zheng Liu [16], representing Cardiff University (UK) and Nanjing University of Science and Technology (Nanjing, China), assessed the level of influence of UK and Chinese public policy on the innovative development of their creative industries, identified the key elements of open, closed and social innovation within the creative economy.

Chinese researchers have highlighted the advantages of large Chinese cities in enhancing the productivity of creative industries. They concluded that the disparity in the distribution of creative industry productivity between large and small Chinese cities is driven by agglomeration economies rather than the enterprises available in the area. They assessed the impact of creative industry clusters on the development of culture and the creative economy in Shanghai and elaborated a project for the development of cultural and creative industries in the Qinba Mountains of Southern Shaanxi. The above aspects are covered in publications by C.-Y. Ho and Y. Sheng [15], J. Zheng and R. Chan [18], and L. Cui, S. Wei, K. Wang, S. Yuan, M. Lei, and K. Cheng [14].

Rinku Gupta [17], a scholar from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences (Mumbai, India), used quantile regression in his research to identify key groups of factors determining the wages of workers in the creative industry. He demonstrated that men earn significantly more than women.

Despite the scientific significance of these studies, certain aspects focused on the development of creative industries as a basic vector of economic growth and employment need further study.

Methods and Methodology

The methodological basis of the conducted research is the practice-proven provisions and

developments, revealing the prerequisites, regularities of formation and development of creative industries; provisions of federal normative-legal acts, which are devoted to the issues of state support of the analyzed industries; applied research of domestic and foreign organizations, which are devoted to individual provisions of their development.

The instrumental methodological foundation of the research includes general scientific methods such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and statistical data analysis. The conducted research has enabled the examination of creative industries in Russia as a fundamental vector for economic growth and employment.

Results

Russia dynamically implements measures aimed to realize of the developed Concept¹, according to the forecast values of which the proportion of creative industries in the country's economy will increase to 6 % by 2030, while the level of creative employment (especially women, young people, and people with disabilities) will increase to 15 % by the same year. Increase the proportions of creative industries and creative (artistic) entrepreneurship in Russia as a whole in the structure of world exports to 3.5 % by 2030.

Creative industries, which generate added value by converting ideas and creativity into products and services, are a crucial resource for both the economic and innovative development of Russia as a whole and its individual regions. Given the global trend towards economic innovation and creativity, Russia has identified the use of creative industries as a resource base for its innovative development as one of the mechanisms for achieving sustainable economic growth.

The potential of Russia's 17 major creative industries (IT and video games; education; design; fashion; publishing, etc.) lies in the breadth of labor opportunities and potential collaborations that can be productively exploited.

It should be noted that creative industries serve as an effective source of sustainable inclusive

1 Concept for the Development of Creative Industries and Mechanisms for Their State Support in Major and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030. 2021. URL: <https://docs.cntd.ru/document/608746222> (Accessed on September 15, 2024) (In Russ.).

growth, because they provide additional opportunities for self-development and are focused on the formation of a favorable living environment.

Currently, the following priority areas of creative industries are identified as the basic vector of Russia's economic growth: increasing the involvement of women, youth, and people with disabilities in creative professions; enhancing the capitalization of intangible assets in Russian businesses, among other initiatives¹.

Figure 1 shows the contribution of Russia's creative economy to GDP among the BRICS+ countries of which it is a member, %.

According to the data reflected in Figure 1, Russia shares the third ranking position with the United Arab Emirates (3,5 %) in the contribution of the creative economy to GDP, while Ethiopia (4,7 %) and China (4,6 %) hold the leading positions.

Fig. 1. The Contribution of Russia's Creative Economy to GDP Among BRICS+ Countries, %²

*no data available

Russia ranks similarly (6.6 %) by the level of employment in the creative industries, with India in second place (8.3 %) and China in first place (9.46 %)³.

In terms of the export of creative industry goods (including print media, design products, new media goods, handicrafts, etc.), Russia is ranked fourth with \$ 1,58 billion, behind China (\$ 220 billion), India (\$ 13,785 billion), and the United Arab Emirates (\$ 9,129 billion)⁴.

Under current conditions, Russia aims to realize the economic potential of its creative industries in all regions, taking into account their unique characteristics and specificities.

Figure 2 shows top 15 Russian regions ranked according to the level of economic development of creative industries.

Fig. 2. Top 15 Russian Regions by the Level of Economic Development of Creative Industries⁵

The analysis of Figure 2 concludes that the highest concentration of creative industry development is observed in Moscow, Tyumen Oblast, and Saint Petersburg, while Perm Krai rounds out the list. These regions significantly surpass other Russian regions in terms of the economic scale of creative industries development.

Creative employment of the Russian population can be assessed by taking into account the following components:

- 1) creative (artistic) industries;
- 2) creative professions.

1 Concept for the Development of Creative Industries and Mechanisms for Their State Support in Major and Largest Urban Agglomerations Until 2030. 2021. URL: <https://docs.cntd.ru/document/608746222> (Accessed on September 15, 2024) (In Russ.).

2 Prospects for the Development of Creative Economies in BRICS+ Countries. 2024. URL: <https://assets.kept.ru/upload/pdf/2024/05/ru-creative-industries-brics-countries-kept-survey.pdf> (Accessed on September 17, 2024) (In Russ.).

3 Ibid

4 Ibid

5 Creative Specializations of Russian Cities: Special Issue. 2022. URL: https://www.hse.ru/data/2022/02/16/1747086382/Human_Capital_NCMU_Digest_Special_Issue_Creative_Cities_02-2022.pdf (Accessed on September 18, 2024) (In Russ.).

Fig. 3 presents the groups of the employed population in the Russian labor market, taking into account the peculiarities of the development of the above-mentioned components.

Fig. 3. Groups of the employed population in the labor market taking into account creative industries as well as creative professions¹

It was found that in the Russian labor market more than 5 million people were involved in the creative economy (over the last five years the number of such employed people has increased by 1.5 million).

Figure 4 shows top 15 Russian regions ranked according to the share of employees in creative industries in the total employment of the region.

Analysis of Figure 4 shows that Moscow, Saint Petersburg, and Tyumen Oblast are leaders in the share of employees working in organizations related to the creative industries and concentrate a significant proportion of creative industry workers.

The study revealed that within the structure of creative employment in Russia, marketing and advertising specialists account for 25 % and programmers for 20 % whereas 55 % of the creative class includes professionals from such fields as designers, photographers, musicians, etc.

Fig. 4. Top 15 Russian Regions by the Share of Employees in Creative Industries²

The leading positions in Russia’s employment are occupied by the fashion industry (over 30 % of the employed), as well as cultural and leisure activities, music and performing arts (28 % of the employed).

More than 80 % of Russia’s employed population in creative professions performs their labor activity in organizations that have the status of a legal entity; while 10 % work for private individuals or as part of household businesses, and 8 % are involved in entrepreneurial activities. Notably, only half of the creative professionals are working in positions directly related to their specialty³.

It has been found that employers hiring creative professionals primarily focus on practical skills directly related to the job and key digital competencies.

Russia’s creative class is concentrated in Moscow, St. Petersburg (over 40 % in creative employment), millionaire cities (other than Moscow and St. Petersburg) – 14 %; large cities – 16 %, towns – 10 %, other Russian cities – about 19 %.

In the course of this study, a workload coefficient for those employed in creative industries was calculated for the period from early 2019 to early 2023, allowing to assess their impact on the employment process. Based on the obtained result, it was found that, on average, for every thousand

1 Creative Class of Russia: A Portrait in Numbers. 2022. URL: <https://www.hse.ru/mirror/pubs/share/807171541.pdf> (Accessed on September 18, 2024) (In Russ.).

2 Ibid

3 Ibid

employed people in Russia, there were 62 individuals employed in creative industries. Furthermore, a significant increase in the coefficient (by 1,3 times) was observed at the beginning of 2023 compared to the beginning of 2019, which is related to the increasing number of the employed in creative industries.

Conclusion

The study concluded that in recent years, the creative economy has emerged as a highly promising key sector, with creative industries exerting an increasing influence on various aspects of modern society and playing a significant role in the economic development. The government views creative industries as a new vector for the growth

of Russia's economy and employment, while the modern business environment is focused on creating commercially successful products that generate profit.

The key trends that allow creative industries to actively develop represent a fairly effective tool that is aimed at the optimal socio-economic development of Russia as a whole and its constituent entities in particular.

Collaboration between government agencies, representatives of creative industries, as well as other ecosystem elements of the creative industry in the country could form the foundation for the realization of significant creative projects, as well as influence the process of stimulating and facilitating change across Russia's economy.

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